

Title: Privacy vs. Security vs. Convenience in the IoT World

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Abstract

How do we balance the desire for privacy with the need for security and protection, knowing that we freely give up personal data for convenience? How irrational are we about the tradeoff between what we say we want for security and how we actually behave? We recognize that data about us is being collected everywhere through cameras, microphones, sensors and online interactions. This continues to increase in the expanding IoT world. Do we “give up” on what data about us is collected and instead focus on limiting how and where our data can be used?

AIM:

Explore the thought-provoking issues around the complex intersection between privacy, security and convenience. Where are we now and where are we headed?

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Dr Coggeshall has been a leading presenter on privacy and identity security, and has been building machine learning consumer behavior models for more than 20 years. He is an expert at predicting consumer behavior, availability of consumer data, fraud and identity dynamics.

CONCLUSIONS:

- People will continue to desire customized interactions and get over the creepy factor.
- We will focus more on how data is used rather than what data is collected.
- We will allow official agencies access to our data for appropriate purposes with oversight.
- Privacy will continue to evolve. Last frontier is what you think?

KEYWORDS:

Privacy, Security, Consumer behavior, Data collection

BIOGRAPHY:

Dr. Stephen Coggeshall is the retired Chief Analytics and Science Office for Lifelock and ID Analytics, companies that protect both consumers and businesses from Identity Fraud. He is a frequent keynote speaker on issues ranging from Privacy, Identity Fraud and Predictive

Analytics in the business world. He spent 11 years doing fusion research at Los Alamos National Laboratory, and then moved into applied machine learning, cofounding three predictive analytics companies. He spent two years inventing and managing novel options trading algorithms at Morgan Stanley, and has consulted extensively in financial services. He is coauthor of the technical book *Foundations of Predictive Analytics*. Currently Dr. Coggeshall is teaching Fraud Analytics at USC Marshall and UCSD Rady business schools.